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Technical note on SEDF requirement

**Michael Höpfner¹, Felix Friedl-Vallon¹, Bernd Funke²,
Anne Kleinert¹, Peter Preusse³, Jörn Ungermann³**

¹Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany

²Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía (CSIC), Gta. de la Astronomía, s/n, 18008 Granada, Spain

³Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ), Wilhelm-Johnen-Straße, 52428 Jülich, Germany

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<p>This document supports the definition of the vertical SEDF knowledge and performance requirements related to the near- and the far-field. These are supported by first 1d linear L2 retrievals.</p>		
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<i>Names of authors</i>		
Michael Höpfner, Felix Friedl-Vallon, Bernd Funke, Anne Kleinert, Peter Preusse, Jörn Ungermann		
<i>ESA Technical Officer</i> Alex Hoffmann Division Mission Science Division Directorate Directorate of Earth Observation Programmes	<i>ESA budget heading</i>	

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V3.0	27-Oct-2024	Update SEDF far-field knowledge requirement from cross-talk- to SEDF-knowledge requirement supported by new linear uncertainty estimations
V4.0	30-Oct-2024	Add further plots with different perturbation ranges in far-field equivalent to the new knowledge requirements
V5.0	5-Nov-2024	Add equations being introduced in v2+ but gotten lost in v3. Correct range numbering in Table 2. Correct Figs. 9,10.
V6.0	25-Nov-2024	Add updates wrt MRD latest requirements

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1. Definition of SEDF and cross-talk: proposed update of formulations in 'EE11 CAIRT: TERMS AND DEFINITIONS DOCUMENT'

Reference: [1]

1.1. SEDF

System Energy Distribution Function (SEDF)	<p>The System Energy Distribution Function (SEDF) describes the spatial distribution in object space of the photons that are collected when measuring a spatial sample i,j and spectral sample k, assuming a spectrally uniform (white) scene with constant spectral radiance $L(x,y)$. It relates $L_k(x,y)$, the spectral integral of the radiance $L(x,y)$ over the bandwidth of spectral sample k, to the measured radiance L'_{ijk}:</p> $L'_{ijk} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} SEDF_{ijk}(x,y) L_k(x,y) dx dy$ <p>where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $SEDF_{ijk}(x,y)$ is the System Energy Distribution Function for spatial sample i,j in a spectral channel k. • x and y correspond to the position of the spatial sample in the instrument object space; each observed tangent point in vertical and across-track direction corresponds to a specific set of (x,y) coordinates. <p>The SEDF includes any displacement of the instrument line-of-sight over the acquisition time of an along-track sample. The SEDF is normalised to unity in object space:</p> $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} SEDF_{ijk}(x,y) dx dy = 1$ <p>The SEDF of spatial sample (i,j) and spectral sample k is calculated by projecting the detector pixel(s) associated with the spatial sample i through the instrument back to object space. The SEDF is defined at the tangent point of the spatial sample. Additional Earth curvature effects (curvature of the horizon), in particular in the across-track direction, are not accounted for in the SEDF.</p> <p>The SEDF is determined by the pixel(s) response function, detector cross-talk, optical Point Spread Functions (diffraction, aberrations, ...) and platform contributions (jitter and drifts).</p> <p>Vertical/Horizontal SEDF:</p>
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	<p>The Vertical/Horizontal SEDF are defined through the centre of a spatial sample as the cross-section in the vertical/ACT direction of the SEDF, obtained such that it contains the SEDF barycentre, and normalised such that its integral is unity.</p> $SEDF_{VER,ijk}(x) = \int_{y=-\infty}^{+\infty} SEDF_{ijk}(x,y) \cdot dy$ $SEDF_{HOR,ijk}(y) = \int_{x=-\infty}^{+\infty} SEDF_{ijk}(x,y) \cdot dx$ <p>E.g. with respect to Figure 8: the vertical SEDF of a sample is measured along a line between H-3,10 and H-3,8 and the horizontal SEDF align a line between H-2,9 and H-4,9, respectively.</p> <p>Vertical/Horizontal Resolution:</p> <p>The vertical/horizontal resolution of the instrument is the FWHM of the vertical/horizontal SEDF.</p>
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Proposed changes:

- Do not include LOS-displacements, i.e. delete formulations:
 - ‘The SEDF includes any displacement of the instrument line-of-sight over the acquisition time of an along-track sample’
 - ‘and platform contributions (jitter and drifts).’
- Add light scattered by the instrument and coming from outside the instrument to the definition of contributions to the SEDF (i.e. photons originating from the instrument and scattered in the instrument should not be considered in the SEDF): ‘(diffraction, aberrations,...)’ → ‘(diffraction, aberrations, scattering of atmospheric light,...)’

1.2. Spatial cross-talk

<p>Spatial cross-talk</p>	<p>The (vertical/horizontal) cross-talk value for the nth neighbour of a sub-sample at the 0th position is the ratio between</p>
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	<p>1) the signal collected by at the n^{th} neighbour when the system is illuminated by a step-scene with radiance values $L_1 > 0$ and $L_2 = 0$ and the step positioned at the centre of the 0^{th} sub-sample</p> <p>and</p> <p>2) the signal collected by a pixel illuminated by a uniform scene with radiance L_1.</p> <p>Equivalently the cross talk at the n^{th} neighbour is</p> $\frac{\int_{(n-\frac{1}{2})p_z}^{(n+\frac{1}{2})p_z} [L_1 \cdot H(z') \otimes SEDF(z')] (z) dz}{\int_{-\frac{p_z}{2}}^{+\frac{p_z}{2}} L_1 dz} = \frac{1}{p_z} \cdot \int_{(n-\frac{1}{2})p_z}^{(n+\frac{1}{2})p_z} [H(z') \otimes SEDF(z')] (z) dz$ <p>Where $[H(z') \otimes SEDF(z')]$ is the convolution of the vertical/horizontal $SEDF(z)$ with the Heaviside function $H(z)$, z is the axis for the vertical/horizontal direction, and p_z is the vertical/horizontal size of the spatial sub-sample.</p>
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We challenge the formula under 2). Since the SEDF is not defined for a point, but for a spatial sample (i.e. it sums up all photons over the whole field which account for the response of the sample), the convolution in the formula is already included in the definition of the SEDF and, therefore, not needed. This is the same formula used by radiative transfer models (e.g. KOPRA, JURASSIC) to simulate the SEDF-effects, only that $L_1 H(z)$ is substituted by the vertical radiance profile $R_\sigma(z)$ in the atmosphere (σ =wavenumber). We also assume, that p_z is the same for all sub-samples which means that either the z -axis is in angular space or referring all to the same tangent height.

We propose this formula instead:

$$Crosstalk(n) = \frac{\int_{-SEDF_{ext}/2}^{+SEDF_{ext}/2} L_1 H(z) SEDF(z - np_z) dz}{\int_{-SEDF_{ext}/2}^{+SEDF_{ext}/2} L_1 SEDF(z) dz} = \int_{-SEDF_{ext}/2}^{+SEDF_{ext}/2} H(z) SEDF(z - np_z) dz$$

Where $SEDF_{ext}$ is the whole extension of the SEDF. The SEDF is assumed to be normalized to one to get to the right side of the equation.

Figure 1 Definition of SEDF.

2. Figures supporting the new formulation of vertical SEDF requirements: far-field

Figure 2 shows the SEDF (as of Eq. (1)) similar to the one used for sensitivity LPE calculations [2]. Here, mainly the 3 inner pixels (-1,0,+1) are Gaussian with FWHM 1.4 km and outside diffraction for a rectangular aperture with aperture height 4 km (@ 700cm⁻¹) is applied.

Outside diffraction for a rectangular aperture with aperture height $D_x=4$ cm (@ 700cm⁻¹) (folded with a rectangular of width $W=1$ km) is applied:

$$\text{SEDF}(x) = \begin{cases} \text{SEDF}_i(x) = \exp\left(-\ln 2 \left(\frac{2x}{FWHM}\right)^2\right), & |x| < x_0 \\ \text{SEDF}_o(x) = \frac{\text{sinc}^2(\pi\sigma D_x \sin x) \otimes \Pi\left(\frac{x}{W}\right)}{\int_{-W/2}^{+W/2} \text{sinc}^2(\pi\sigma D_x \sin x) dx}, & |x| \geq x_0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

x : elevation angle [rad], D_x : aperture height [cm], σ : wavenumber [cm⁻¹], FWHM: full-width at half maximum of the Gaussian [rad], W : size of sub-sample [rad], $\Pi(x/W)$: rectangular with width W , x_0 : intersection between $\text{SEDF}_i(x)$ and $\text{SEDF}_o(x)$.

The denominator in $\text{SEDF}_o(x)$ is a normalization factor such that $\text{SEDF}_o(0) = 1$.

The elevation angle x [rad] is converted into units of [km] in the following figures by using a satellite altitude $H_{\text{sat}} = 800$ km, a reference tangent altitude $H_{\text{tref}} = 5$ km and an Earth radius $R_e = 6370$ km by:

$$x[\text{km}] = x[\text{rad}] \sqrt{(R_e + H_{\text{sat}})^2 - (R_e + H_{\text{tref}})^2} \quad (2)$$

Figure 2 SEDF used for cross-talk estimation. 3 inner pixels Gauss with FWHM 1.4 km; outside diffraction with aperture height 4 km (@ 700cm⁻¹). Mind that here an infinite small sub-sample width has been used such that the small 'wiggles' of the diffraction pattern can be seen. This is taken into account in the updated version (see chapter 6).

The following Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the cross-talk for the applied (baseline) SEDF in the LPE calculations (which accounted for diffraction of 4 cm aperture), the numbers proposed for the performance requirement. The thin bars as well as the blue curve are the values for the cross-talk of 1-km pixels, while the thick bars are the summed up cross-talk over 20-km wide sections. The thin bars as well as the blue curve are the values for the cross-talk of 1-km pixels, while the thick bars are the summed up cross-talk over 20-km wide sections.

The proposal is to add to the baseline SEDF (Eq. (1), Figure 2) cross-talk, for pixels outside the 3rd one, a value of 0.0002 per km to account for straylight. For pixels 1,2,3 the baseline SEDF cross-talk is multiplied by 1.5 not to deviate too strongly from the MATER requirements.

Figure 3 Cross-talk calculated with the SEDF in Figure 2. Black line: per sample, numbers in broad bars: per 20 km bin.

Figure 4 As Figure 3 but added 0.0002 per km in case of the 20-km sections, for the proposed performance requirement (to account for additional e.g. straylight effects).

3. Figures supporting the new formulation of vertical SEDF requirements: near-field

Central part (samples 0,1):

The central part (middle and 1st pixels) of the standard SEDF (Figure 2) is a Gaussian and in the original MATER knowledge [3] requirement 'knowledge shall be better than 1% [goal: $\leq 0.5\%$] of its peak value' is required. This has been tested by LPE calculations using a 1% uncertainty of the FWHM of a Gaussian with FWHM of 1.4 km. The results demonstrated that this requirement leads to retrieval uncertainties lower than many other instrumental knowledge uncertainties tested [4]. Therefore, we propose to change the requirement to a 2% knowledge requirement of the half-width of the central part and leave the performance requirement to 1.4 km. (Update to 1.5 km: see tech-note 'DEL-11-TN4j_SEDF_1500m_vs_1400m').

Samples 2,3:

The standard SEDF cross-talk is smaller than the original MATER requirement (Figure 7), but the required performance is very similar to the MATER (Figure 8).

Figure 5 Inner part of the baseline SEDF (Gauss, blue) and the difference to the SEDF with FWHM perturbed by 1%.

Figure 6 Change of cross-talk of the 1st pixel when the FWHM is perturbed by 1% as in Figure 5

Figure 7 Cross-talk calculated with the SEDF in Figure 2 for inner samples.

Figure 8 As Figure 7 but for performance requirements.

4. Uncertainty estimation for SEDF far-field knowledge requirements

To estimate the uncertainty introduced by an incorrect knowledge about the shape of the far-field SEDF function, linear retrieval tests were performed. The applied perturbations of the SEDF-function are illustrated in Figure 9. The baseline SEDF is changed in seven different altitude regions (see Table 1). In each of these regions the SEDF was perturbed by a factor of 1.5 relative to the baseline SEDF.

Table 1: Perturbed vertical parts of the SEDF.

Index (see Figure 9)	Perturbed region of the SEDF	Related vertical samples (0=central)	Mean Perturbation value (relative to SEDF central maximum)
0	2.5-7.5 km	3-7	2.4e-3
1	7.5-17.5 km	8-17	3.4e-4
2	17.5-37.5 km	18-37	7.1e-5
3	37.5-57.5 km	38-57	2.5e-5
4	57.5-77.5 km	58-77	1.5e-5
5	77.5-97.5 km	78-97	1.1e-5
6	97.5-117.5 km	98-117	0.9e-5

For each of these seven perturbations, perturbation spectra of whole vertical limb-sequences have been calculated (i.e. difference spectra with-without perturbation) for the April+45_day atmosphere using the linear SWB instrument simulator 'instsim.py'.

These perturbation spectra were the baseline for 1-d linear error analysis which was performed for all species, for different microwindow datasets and different prescribed vertical resolution (goal, goal+500m, and threshold). In the following, we will discuss the results related to the threshold vertical resolution as the baseline for performance calculation. Still, all other Figures are available.

Results of the linear retrievals are shown in Figure 15 to Figure 20 for the L2 parameters as vertical profiles of the estimated uncertainty due to SEDF knowledge uncertainty relative to the L2 threshold values. In Figure 15, Figure 17, and Figure 19 the perturbations as in Figure 9 and Table 1 were applied while in Figure 16, Figure 18, and Figure 20 the baseline perturbations were raised by a factor of 10.

From those Figures, one can see that the most affected parameters are temperature, water vapour, ozone, SF6, HNO3 and PAN. SF6 and PAN are mainly influenced by the SEDF knowledge uncertainty of SEDF regions 0, 1 and 2 (i.e. up to 37.5 km from the SEDF center). HNO3, O3, and H2O also by #3 and slightly by #4. In case of temperature, SEDF parts 4, 5 and 6 affect only the top altitude region.

Figure 21 to Figure 26 compare the results for temperature, H2O, O3, HNO3, PAN, and SF6 using different sets of microwindows. Especially for H2O (e.g. using mwMIPesa) and O3 (e.g. using CAIRTlarge) this shows, that a reduction of the retrieval uncertainty mainly for the inner SEDF ranges and at lower altitudes is possible. For temperature, the induced uncertainty at the highest altitude layer by SEDF ranges 4, 5, and 6

remains the same, since at these altitudes there is mainly one band delivering information (@~720cm-1). At lowest altitudes, for the SEDF ranges #0 and #1, CAIRTlarge seems to perform better than CAIRTstd but higher up CAIRTstd delivers comparable results.

Figure 9 Perturbation of SEDF function for retrieval uncertainty estimation.

To reduce the different altitude ranges for the knowledge requirement and to add also the altitude range 1.5-2.5 km additional calculation were performed. Here, the perturbation of the SEDF function was done additively, i.e. with a constant value (relative to the SEDF maximum). Details are provided in Table 2 and Figure 10.

The related cross-talk values without and with the perturbations are shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12. Comparing the cross-talk values in Figure 12 to the performance values in Figure 4 shows that for perturbations 1-3, the cross-talk values are just inside the performance limits. Only for perturbation #4, the performance limits are exceeded by the perturbation for cross-talk regions above 20 km by roughly a factor

of 2. Thus, a reduction of this value (#4 in Table 2 from 2e-5 to 1e-5) might be feasible (TBD) and would help the temperature retrieval at high altitudes (see following paragraph).

The related linear retrieval uncertainty estimates are shown in Figure 27 - Figure 29 for the standard microwindow set and in Figure 30 to Figure 32 for the extended microwindow set. The knowledge uncertainty values (Table 2) have been chosen such that the great majority of the L2 uncertainties is less than half the threshold value. The few exceptions are temperature at highest altitudes, ozone at lowest altitudes and PAN. Comparing the results for the two sets of microwindows shows, that for ozone and PAN these results depend much on the set of spectral ranges, allowing for more optimal choices. In case of temperature, further mitigation strategies may be investigated in more detail in the future.

Table 2: Perturbed vertical parts of the SEDF: knowledge requirements.

Index (see Figure 10)	Perturbed region of the SEDF	Related vertical samples (0=central)	Knowledge requirement (relative to SEDF central maximum)
1	1.5-2.5 km	2	2e-2
2	2.5-5.5 km	3-5	1e-2
3	5.5-20.5 km	6-20	5e-4
4	20.5-117.5 km	21-117	2e-5

Figure 10 Perturbation of SEDF function for retrieval uncertainty estimation: knowledge requirements (see Table 2).

Figure 11 Cross-talk of reference SEDF ref from Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Figure 12 Cross-talk of perturbed SEDFs from Figure 10.

5. Linear retrievals for all ERS atmospheres

Linear 1d retrieval tests have been performed for all atmospheres of the ERS dataset on basis of the knowledge requirement values in Table 3. Results are presented now in form of the ‘traffic-light’ plot summarizing the uncertainties with respect to the requirement thresholds (Figure 33).

Table 3: Perturbed vertical parts of the SEDF: knowledge requirements.

Index (see Figure 10)	Perturbed region of the SEDF	Related vertical samples (0=central)	Knowledge requirement (relative to SEDF central maximum)
1	1.5-2.5 km	2	2e-2
2	2.5-5.5 km	3-5	5e-3
3	5.5-20.5 km	6-20	5e-4
4	20.5-117.5 km	21-117	2e-5

6. Updates and new requirement formulation

As can be seen in Figure 33, for a few parameters (Tlos, H2O, O3, SF6), the resulting uncertainties are still larger or near their threshold requirements. Therefore, for the final set of knowledge requirements which have been flowing into the MRD requirement formulation and the threshold 2d performance estimation, the numbers provided in Table 4 have been proposed. Application of these numbers to the instrument performance are reported in [5].

An update of Eq. (1) of this document is provided in Eq. (4) in the SWB ATBD document [6]: here a scattering part (sc) has been added to the diffraction function in the outer field of the SEDF. Further updates of Figure 2 of the present document are provided in Figure 13. These updates have been done to correct for the fact that in the SEDF shown in Figure 2 here above, the convolution of the diffraction function with the rectangular function simulating the size of the sub-sample width was not taken into consideration.

Figure 13 Example for a vertical SEDF as vertical distance around the tangent point, including the far-field (blue, in log-scale) and focused around the nearest neighbors (orange, in linear scale); here, $x_0 = 1.5$ km, FWHM = 1.5 km, $D_x = 4$ cm, $W = 1$ km. For different scattering contributions: $sc = 0$, left; $sc = 10^{-5}$, middle; $sc = 10^{-4}$, right.

Figure 14 Cross-talk values belonging to the SEDF functions in Figure 13.

Table 4: Proposed vertical SEDF knowledge requirements.

Perturbed region of the SEDF	Knowledge requirement (relative to SEDF central maximum)
1.5-2.5 km	1e-2
2.5-5.5 km	5.3e-4
5.5-20.5 km	6.1e-5
20.5-60.5 km	2e-5
>60.5 km	5e-6

Performance:

- The vertical FWHM of the System Energy Distribution Function (SEDF) shall be ≤ 1.4 km below 80 km of altitude, and ≤ 3 km above. For wavenumbers <780 cm^{-1} , a FWHM of ≤ 1.5 km is possible (see [7]).
- The vertical spatial crosstalk shall be $\leq 9\%$ for the first neighbour, $\leq 3\%$ for the second neighbour $\leq 2\%$ for the third neighbour
- Outside the 3rd neighbour, the vertical spatial crosstalk shall be below the values provided in Figure 14 (middle: goal, right: threshold) for 20 km broad intervals.

Knowledge:

- The vertical FWHM of the System Energy Distribution Function (SEDF) shall be known better than 2%.
- See Table 4.

Figure 15 Retrieval profile uncertainty relative to L2 threshold values at different altitude regions induced by perturbation of the far-field SEDF for atmosphere April+45_day. The vertical resolution was set to the threshold values. The CAIRT standard microwindows were applied. The different columns are related to the different

perturbation regions (see Table 1). High-resolved error profiles are shown as green lines. Thick black vertical lines denote the mean errors in that altitude region as defined in the L2 requirement table

Figure 16 As Figure 15 but for perturbations enhanced by a factor of 10.

Figure 17 As Figure 15 but for further species.

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Figure 21 Like Figure 15 but only for temperature comparing different microwindow sets for 10 times increased knowledge uncertainties compared to those provided in Figure 9 and Table 1.

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Figure 25 Like Figure 15 but only for PAN comparing different microwindow sets for 10 times increased knowledge uncertainties compared to those provided in Figure 9 and Table 1.

Figure 26 Like Figure 15 but only for SF6 comparing different microwindow sets for 10 times increased knowledge uncertainties compared to those provided in Figure 9 and Table 1.

Figure 27 Retrieval profile uncertainty relative to L2 threshold values at different altitude regions induced by perturbation of the SEDF for atmosphere April+45_day. The vertical resolution was set to the threshold values. The CAIRT standard microwindows were applied. The different column numbering in the header is related to the different perturbation regions (1-4, columns: 2,3,4, and 5)) (see Table 2). High-resolved error profiles are shown as

green lines. Thick black vertical lines denote the mean errors in that altitude region as defined in the L2 requirement table.

Figure 28 As Figure 27 but for further species.

Figure 29 As Figure 27 but for further species.

Figure 30 Like Figure 27 but for the CAIRTlarge microwindow set.

Figure 31 As Figure 30 but for further species.

Figure 32 As Figure 30 but for further species.

Figure 33 Linear 1d uncertainty estimation based on all ERS atmospheres for the SEDF knowledge assumptions from Table 3.

7. References

- [1] CAIRT Terms, 'EE11 CAIRT: TERMS AND DEFINITIONS DOCUMENT', EOP-FMP/2021-11-2309 Version 2, May 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://bwsyncandshare.kit.edu/s/6rLFbBMYWqQpcGM>
- [2] M. Höpfner, B. Funke, F. Friedl-Vallon, and J. Ungermann, 'DEL-09.4-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-4.0 – Technical note on diffraction/far field SEDF - Version 4', DEL-09.4-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-4.0, July 2024.
- [3] CAIRT MATER, 'EE-11 CANDIDATE MISSION CAIRT, MISSION ASSUMPTION AND TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS (MATER)', EOP-ΦMP/2021-11-2308, Revision 4, Nov. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://bwsyncandshare.kit.edu/s/PSxgEkcTFsSCpMn>
- [4] M. Garcia-Comas, B. Funke, M. Lopez-Puertas, and M. Höpfner, 'Supplement to DEL-08-02-TN4-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC_1.3 -Non-LTE error assessment for CAIRT', Suppl. DEL-08-02-TN4-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC_1.3, Sept. 2023.
- [5] M. Höpfner, B. Funke, P. Preusse, Q. Errera, B.-M. Sinnhuber, and J. Ungermann, 'DEL-09-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.0 – CAIRT measurement requirements assessment - Technical Note TN-3', DEL-09-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-v2.0, July 2025.
- [6] M. Höpfner, B. Funke, Q. Errera, P. Raspollini, B.-M. Sinnhuber, and J. Ungermann, 'CAIRT linear SWB ATBD', DEL-04-01a-ATBD-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.0, Sept. 2025.
- [7] M. Höpfner and B. Funke, 'DEL-09.5-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0 – Technical note on L2 performance for FOV widths 1.4 km vs 1.5 km - Version 1', DEL-09.5-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0, Oct. 2024.